

Study of Fetomaternal Outcome in Multifetal GestationAayushi Suthar¹, Payal Panchal², Harsh Suthar³, Svija Ghanchi⁴, Rahil Ghanchi⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. NHLMMC²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Smt. NHLMMC³Medical Student, NHLMMC⁴MS Obstetrics and Gynecology⁵Medical Student, HNGU

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: A multiple pregnancy may be the result of the fertilization of a simple egg that splits to create identical fetuses or it may be the result of the fertilization of multiple eggs that fraternal fetus or it may be the combination of these both.

Aims and Objectives: This prospective study was conducted over one year aimed to investigate the fetal and maternal outcome in multifetal gestation. The study included women with multiple pregnancy at or after 26 weeks of gestation who delivered in our hospital, excluding women with multiple pregnancy delivering at gestational age less than 26 weeks.

Results: In this study, the incidence of dichorionic diamniotic twins were more as compared to other multifetal pregnancies. As the age advances in multiparous patients, incidence of dichorionic twins was more compared to monochorionic twins. Majority of trichorionic twins were conceived by Invitro fertilization. The most common complication observed was preterm labour in all types of chorionicity. The prevalence of LSCS was the most common mode of delivery in all multifetal patients. Dichorionic twins had better 5 min APGAR score compared to monochorionic and trichorionic twins.

Conclusion: Multifetal pregnancy is a great challenge to the concerned obstetricians. Vigilant antenatal, intrapartum and postnatal care will help in early detection of complications and their management. Liberal use of cesarean delivery, especially in preterm pregnancies, will improve the neonatal prognosis. Hence the need for better obstetric care, neonatal care health services to get a better fruitful outcome.

Keywords: Pregnancy, incidence, prognosis, twin gestation, monochorionic twins, dichorionic twins, trichorionic twins, maternal outcome, fetal outcome, preterm labour, APGAR score.

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Introduction

The term multifetal pregnancies include twins, triplets and higher orders multifetal. Multiple pregnancies are associated with increased risk of obstetric complications as well as prenatal morbidity and mortality especially in developing countries. Multiple pregnancies carry higher risks of adverse fetal and neonatal outcomes and this has consequences for child health as well as for families and the health care system [1]. Multifetal pregnancy result in increased rate of preterm birth (<37wk of gestation) which compromise neonatal survival and increases the risk of neonatal morbidity. 25% of twins and almost 75% of triplets require NICU admission. Threefold increase cerebral palsy is seen in multiple birth babies. [2] In addition to these also there is increase in risk of congenital malformations, abnormal growth and trauma at delivery with multifetal pregnancies. [3] Therefore, multiple birth are considered high risk

and require close monitoring. Multiple pregnancies are associated with increased emotional, personal, financial and social costs in pregnant patients and their families, also there is significant increase in maternal complications such as spontaneous abortion, anemia, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, hydramnios, preterm labor, maternal hemorrhage in form of APH and PPH, caesarean section, obstetric hysterectomy, prolonged hospital stay, blood transfusion in multiple pregnancies than in singletons.[4] Thus increasing maternal morbidity and mortality with increase in number of fetuses [5,6]. In modern obstetrics with advanced ultrasonographic techniques and color Doppler, multiple pregnancy and associated condition like chorionicity, growth discordance, vascular complications, twin to twin transfusion syndrome, intrauterine death of one or more fetus and congenital anomalies can now be diagnosed at

early stage of gestation. [7] Vigilant Obstetric care not only decreases maternal morbidity and mortality but also improve fetal outcome.

Materials and Methods

This is a prospective study of 110 Women with multifetal pregnancy admitted at our institute from September 2022 to September 2023 including all emergency as well as registered patients.

Inclusion Criteria: Women with multiple pregnancy at or after 26 week of gestation who delivered in our hospital.

Exclusion Criteria: Women with multiple pregnancy, delivering at gestational age less than 26 week of gestation.

Study was conducted to 1) Analyze the epidemiology of multifetal gestation. 2) To study maternal and fetal outcome in patients of multifetal pregnancies according to their chorionicity. 3) Early diagnosis of maternal and fetal complications

and their management in multiple pregnancy.

In all patients detailed history was taken including age, parity, menstrual and obstetric history, past, family and personal history. Clinical examination including systemic and obstetric examinations, with all required investigations was done. The mode of delivery of babies, associated maternal and fetal complications, type of interference and complications of third stage were noted. APGAR score at 1 and 5 minutes and resuscitation measures if required were noted. Birth weight was noted, gender of babies (isosexuals /heterosexuals), iud/stillbirth/live, admission to NICU of babies and neonatal complications of babies in terms of death in nicu. Pediatric consultation was obtained as per requirement.

Data analysis is carried out using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 10.5) package.

Results

Table 1: Age Distribution According To. Their Chorionicity

Chorionicity	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
DCDA	87	18	41	26.11	4.766
MCDA	17	21	35	25.82	4.374
MCMA	3	21	28	25	3.512
TCTA	3	23	33	28	5.000

Mean age in DCDA group was 26.11 +/- 2 (4.766) whereas the mean age in MCDA group is 25.82 +/- 2 (4.374) with significant p value of. (<0.05) with 95% CI. DCDA twins were seen in more advanced age group than MCDA.

Table 2: Mode of Conception

	MCDA+MCMA (N-20) (%)	DCDA (N-87) (%)	TCTA (N-3) (%)
Spontaneous Conception	15 (75%)	68 (78.16%)	1 (33.33%)
Ovulation Induction	3 (15%)	9 (10.34%)	0
IVF Conception	2 (10%)	10 (11.50%)	2 (66.67%)

75 % of monochorionic twins, 78.16% of DCDA had spontaneous conception and 33.33% trichorionic triamniotic had spontaneous conception. 10.34 % of dichorionic and 15 % of Monochorionic conceived after ovulation

induction. Where in monochorionic and dichorionic IVF conception rate is almost equal. But in trichorionic there is significantly higher conception rate with IVF compare to Monochorionic and dichorionic.

Table 3: The Association of Multifetal Gestation and Their Complications.

Complications	MCDA+MCMA (N-20) (%)	DCDA (N-87) (%)	TCTA (N-3) (%)
Preterm	14 (70%)	62 (71.26%)	3 (100%)
Anaemia	4 (20%)	25 (28.73%)	1 (33.33%)
Hypertensive Disorders Of Pregnancy	8 (40%)	29 (33.33%)	1 (33.33%)
APH	2 (10%)	2 (2.29%)	0
DM	1 (5%)	5 (5.74%)	0
Prom	4 (20%)	12 13.79%	1 (33.33%)
Cord Prolapse	1 (5%)	1 (1.14%)	0
PPH	2 (10%)	10 (11.49%)	0
Hydramnios	2 (10%)	9 (10.34%)	1 (33.33%)

The most common complication observed was preterm labour in all type of chorionicity. In trichorionic pregnancy preterm is observed in 100% of cases.

Table 4: Indications of LSCS

	MCDA+MCMA	DCDA
Malpresentation	6 (30%)	24 (27.58%)
PROM+NPOL	4 (20%)	4 (4.59%)
PREVCS	1 (5%)	13 (14.94%)
Fetal Distress	0	4 (4.59%)
Cord Prolapse	1 (5%)	1 (1.14%)
Eclampsia	1 (5%)	3 (3.44%)
APH	2 (10%)	2 (2.29%)

Most common indication of LSCS were malpresentation in both Monochorionic as well as dichorionic. 2nd common indication of LSCS was Prevecs in dichorionic whereas PROM+NPOL in monochorionic twins.

Table 5: Relation between Apgar score and chorionicity.

	MCDA+ MCMA (N-39) (%)	DCDA (N-166) (%)	TCTA (N-9) (%)	X2 VALUE	'P' VALUE
<4	3 (7.69%)	13 (7.83%)	1 (11.11%)	1.704	0.789
4-7	16 (41.02%)	54 (32.53%)	4 (44.44%)		
>7	20 (51.28%)	99 (59.63%)	4 (44.44%)		

In present study, dichorionic had better APGAR score compared to monochorionic and trichorionic. P value between these two groups was found 0.789 (< 0.05) which was statistically not significant.

Table 6: Gender of the Newborn According To Their Chorionicity.

	Gender of The Newborn		X2 Value	'P' Value
	Isosexuals	Heterosexuals		
MCDA+ MCMA (N-20) (%)	18 (90%)	2(10%)	15.71	0.00038
DCDA (N-87) (%)	36 (41.36%)	51 (58.64%)		
TCTA (N-3) (%)	1 (33.33%)	2(66.66%)		
Total (110)	55	55		

In DCDA group, 41.34% had isosexuals and 58.62 % had heterosexuals. In MCDA group, 80% had isosexuals and 20% had heterosexuals. In MCMA 100% were isosexuals. It is statistically significant with p value of 0.00038 (<0.05). In twins with monochorionic placenta, there is increased isosexuals.

Discussion

This study was conducted on 110 multifetal pregnancies with the aim to study the maternal and perinatal outcome in according to their chorionicity. In present study 79.09% were DCDA, 15.45 % were MCDA, 2.72% were MCMA and 2.72% were TCTA.

In this study, the mean age distribution of DCDA was 26.11+ 4.766, MCDA was 25.82 + 4.374 and MCMA was 25 + 3.512 with 95% CI. It was statistically significant. 78.16 % of DCDA twins, 75 % of MCDA+MCMA twins had spontaneous conception.

There was no difference with regard to mode of conception between monochorionic and dichorionic pregnancies. This result was similar to the study by Assuncao et al [8] and Lata singh et al,[9] 74.7 % had preterm labour, 32 % had hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, 44 % had anemia and 13.33 % had PPH. In present study MC pregnancies, a 5-minute APGAR score of less than 7 was found in

48.71 and 40.36 % of DC pregnancies. The P value between the two groups was found not significant 0.789. The APGAR score was found to be less in MC pregnancies similar to the study results of Naushaba et [10] also.

Conclusion

Strengthening the antenatal care facilities at the grassroots level will help in timely diagnosis and referral of patients with multiple pregnancy to tertiary centers. Diagnosis of multifetal pregnancy and determination of chorionicity is essential to anticipated abnormalities of monochorionicity. Although ART is a boon to infertile couple, there is an unprecedented increase in the higher order births. Multiple gestation is a high risk pregnancy associated with increase in maternal and fetal complications, thus it requires optimum obstetrics resuscitation facilities and intense neonatal care to improve maternal and neonatal outcome. The knowledge of maternal and fetal complications helps in better surveillance, and in prevention of the morbidity and adverse outcome.

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